

Sustainable Employability through the Lens of the Shrimad Bhagavad Gita: Ancient Wisdom for the Future Workforce

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Rapid changes in the business environment such as rapid advancement in technology, globalization, and varying migration policies offer various challenges for individuals in sustaining their employability. Companies easily move to other countries for the want of a cheaper workforce. As today's world is driven by material goals, competition among companies has become intense. Hence individual is not only required to be employable, but the focus has shifted to sustainable employability. However, research in this area is lacking. This paper examines how the Srimad Bhagavad Gita can improve sustainable employability. The Bhagavad Gita consists of wisdom to attain the highest state of self-consciousness. As sustainable employability requires a person to be self-confident, competent, motivated, and emotionally stable, the discourse of Lord Krishna in the Bhagavad Gita is the only correct way to develop these qualities. Unfortunately, there is a paucity of awareness regarding the lessons given in Bhagavad Gita. This research aims to explore the significance of the Bhagavad Gita to provide sustainable solutions to humanity. The Bhagavad Gita guides individuals to know themselves and gives them the ability to decide right or wrong. Mindfulness, emotional intelligence, and positivity are some of the benefits offered by the sheer wisdom of the Bhagavad Gita, hence making individuals employable while maintaining their well-being at the same time.

Keywords: Bhagavad Gita, globalization, global interconnectedness, sustainable employability

The contemporary business environment is shifting from the old economy to the new economy. Sharma and Sharma (2019) called it the 'gig economy'. Labour markets worldwide have undergone dynamic changes due to technological advancement, globalization, and immutable labour movements (Pham & Jackson, 2020). The economy is becoming less competitive for workers with traditional abilities, while the need for people with new skills has increased dramatically (Arokiasamy et al., 2024). Moreover, a lack of skilled staff can make it harder to replace under-skilled employees (Courchesne et al., 2025).

Globalisation has connected the entire world into a single 'world system'. It has created challenges for organisations regarding their growth and sustainability (Parthasarathi, Reddy, & Rao, 2018). The roots of globalisation can be traced back five thousand years, as indicated by Vedic history. The only difference is that business markets drive today's globalisation process, whereas in Vedic times it was propelled by mutual desires and the healthy exchange of ideas

(Krishna, 2011).

Singh and Ehlers (2020) also highlighted the structural changes in the labour market brought about by globalisation and the Industrial Revolution. These changes act as a double-edged sword. On the one hand, they offer graduates alternative job opportunities both domestically and internationally (Lee & Clarke, 2019). However, these modifications also result in underemployment, economic uncertainty, and job insecurity (Dean & Wilson, 2009). This requires graduates to manage their career trajectories effectively. Moreover, governments and higher education are also under an obligation to prepare their students for a better future (Jackson & Wilton, 2017).

Employability

There are multiple concepts of employability. This concept has travelled through many phases since the twentieth century, resulting in multiple definitions and operationalisations (Guilbert, Bernard, Gouvernet, & Rossier, 2016). Employability's first publication came in the 1950s when it was seen as a tool for achieving full employment. The primary focus was on characteristics such as disposition towards the job and self-worth, and only unemployed people were offered opportunities to join the labour force (Forrier & Sels, 2003). In the decade of the 1970s, economic changes led to a shift in the concept's focus to knowledge and skills. In the 1980s, employability emerged as a key human resource tool that helps match demand and supply in a changing organisational environment (Thijssen, Heijden, & Rocco, 2008). Since the 1990s, employability has emerged as an alternative tool to job insecurity. It mainly focuses on career possibilities within and outside of organisations. The employability literature increasingly focuses on a person's capacity to maintain employment in the internal or external job marketplace. According to Forrier and Sels (2003), employability literature now focuses on individuals. The shift in focus on individual-level

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employability has gained considerable momentum. William, Dodd, Steele, and Randall (2016) suggest that an individual's viewpoint on employability is increasingly crucial due to the time and resources needed to establish and sustain it.

Sustainable Employability

Today's corporate world demands flexible employees who can adapt to changing culture. Every individual must constantly endeavor to learn and adapt to contribute to the advancement of society (Parthasarathi et al., 2018). Moreover, Goal 8 of Sustainable Development aims to promote equitable growth in the economy, encompassing effective work and adequate job prospects for all (Arokiasamy, 2024). Sustainability refers to a 'state' of indefinite continuation. It can be defined as the ability to preserve, rejuvenate,

and restore interconnected components of nature, organisation, or society (Jabeen, Nadeem, Raziq, & Sajjad, 2021). This concept covers both natural resource conservation and employee well-being (Wilkinson, Hill, & Gollan, 2001).

Sustainable employability has gained popularity in recent times. Harten (2016) defined it as a combination of adaptability, current knowledge, and awareness of job opportunities. According to Jabeen et al. (2021), employability, work ability, and vitality all contribute to an individual's ability to function efficiently at work. Brouwers, Engels, Heerkens, and van der Beek (2015) understood sustainable employability as employees' ability to contribute in current as well as future jobs while preserving well-being and health. Jabeen et al. (2021) highlight the significance of sustainable employability in public policy discussions and debates in Western European countries. Table 1 provides important definitions of the concept.

Table 1
Important Dimensions of Sustainable Employability

Definition	Dimensions	Sources
Employee's ability to participate in current and future occupations while retaining health and well-being, as well as the circumstances necessary for this to emerge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Motivation ● Resilience ● Social support at work ● Competence ● Physical and mental health 	Brouwers et al. (2015)
Sustainable employability depends on employees' current knowledge, adaptability, and perception of job chances.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Willingness to change ● Up-to-date expertise ● Employment opportunities 	Harten (2016)
Sustainable employability is an Individual's entire ability and possibility of working continuously through motivation in workable conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Employability ● Vitality ● Work ability (health) 	Semeijn, Caniels, and Kooistra (2019)
Long-term ability to obtain and keep quality jobs while responding to evolving economic and workplace conditions across all phases of life.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Work ability ● Adaptation to Change 	Smyth, Pit and Hansen (2018)
Employees' capacity and commitment to employment presently and in the future.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Work motivation ● Health 	Ybema, Vuuren and Van Dam (2020)

Note. (Source: Author's own elaboration)

The table indicates that there is no commonly recognised understanding of this subject. Yet it is recognised that it includes qualities such as employability, vitality (resilience & willingness to accomplish a job), and work ability. These dimensions, according to De Lange, Kooij, and Heijden (2015), Jabeen et al. (2021), Ybema et al. (2020) are the most relevant for one's long-term employability. This study utilises the teachings of the Bhagavad Gita to explore long-term employability.

The Bhagavad Gita

The Shrimad Bhagavad Gita also known as the Gita, is a seven-hundred-verse Hindu scripture that is a part of the epic Mahabharata (Chapters 23-40 of book 6 of the Mahabharata, also known as the Bhishma Parva) (Davis, 2014). The meaning of Bhagavad Gita is 'The Lord's Song'. It consists of the philosophical preachings of Lord Krishna to encourage the hesitant Arjuna to battle against his siblings. The *Holy Gita* is one of India's most significant contributions to the world (Sharma & Ramachandran, 2015). It represents the ultimate spiritual enigma. The Gita combines the ideas

of the Vedas, Upanishads, and Hinduism core scriptures into a unified way, which provides the foundation of Indian spiritual knowledge. The foundation of all philosophies and doctrines provides a comprehensive understanding of self-realization (Parthasarathi et al., 2018). The significant metaphysical fact advocated by the holy Gita is that the soul is eternal, indestructible, and all-pervasive. Thompson (2011) describes an amalgamation of Vedic ideas based on a belief in the divine. The Bhagavad Gita aligns with the Upanishads, encouraging individuals to strive for perfection in all their endeavours (Tilak, 1935). The profound effect of Gita lessons is not restricted to India but has spread throughout the world. The British Army's seven regiments received a lecture on this holy *granth*, covering topics such as self-mastery, world sustainability, duty, mental control, and fighting methods from the Mahabharata (Parthasarathi, 2018).

Role of Bhagavad Gita in Sustainable Employability

The quality of education strongly determines the nature of civilization. The absence of human values has the potential to plunge

every civilization into disdain, division, and violence. The holy Gita has mentioned two sides in our hearts. The first one is the divine side and the other is the demoniac side. As per preaching by the holy Gita, the divine side can be generated by the cultivation of values. The demoniac side is invoked by contemplating only material things with no spiritual knowledge. If one invokes the divine side, he becomes an angel, otherwise demoniac side creates demons (Krishna, 2011). The ultimate aim of education is to make an individual's life fulfilling and goal-oriented. The university is a turning point in every student's life, when one must make major decisions about their career (Rothwell & Arnold, 2007). The correct decisions cannot be taken without proper knowledge of self and the ability to differentiate right or wrong. The principles of the Bhagavad Gita help an individual in the right decision-making (Patel, 2024).

This study relies upon the conceptual framework of sustainable employability given by Jabeen et al. (2021). The authors used social information processing theory (SIP) and conservation of resource theory (COR) to guide their research.

The personal resources defined by Hobfoll (2002) as per the COR theory are the abilities of the person to cope with challenging situations. Social information processing theory, on the other hand, gave the interconnection between one's social environment and ability to process information (Zalesny & Ford, 1990). The social support resources under this theory have been proven significant for enhancing employability. (Semeijn et al., 2015). Proponents such as Avey, Luthans, and Jensen (2009), Onyishi et al. (2015), and Udayar et al. (2018) indicated a positive impact of personal resources such as psychological capital, core self-evaluations, and emotional intelligence on an individual's employability.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of Sustainable Employability

Note. (Source: Jabeen et al., 2021)

The holy Gita emphasises complex harmony. These concepts are always useful and constitute the unchanging truth of spirituality. It presents information about our best psychological talents that may be validated. These teachings benefit individuals dealing with any

practical dilemma. The teachings of Yoga Shastra can also be implemented in one's life. As a result, it is simple to apply the same to all aspects of human life including employability (Gavade, 2022; Kalia et al., 2025; Karmakar et al., 2025).

Through the Bhagavad Gita, one can eradicate despondency caused by ignorance and can attain unlimited wisdom through sustained learning. It emphasises raising awareness and learning through every action we take (Mishra, Sharma, & Sharma, 2017).

Psychological Capital and Bhagwad Gita

The notion of psychological capital originated in positive psychology, pioneered by Martin Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi in 1994. Luthans, Youssef, and Avolio (2007) defined psychological capital as “an individual's positive psychological state of development that is characterized by: (1) having confidence (self-efficacy) to take on and put in the necessary effort to succeed at challenging tasks; (2) making a positive attribution (optimism) about succeeding now and in the future; (3) persevering toward goals and, when necessary, redirecting paths to goals (hope) to succeed; and (4) when beset by problems and adversity, sustaining and bouncing back and even beyond (resilience) to attain success.” Psychological capital is relevant concerning one's career and work attitudes (Chiesa, Fazi, Guglielmi, & Mariani, 2018). Dabbas and Singh (2018) suggest that Gita's teachings align with positive psychology's emphasis on character development and lead to enhanced strengths.

Salagame (2014) reported that the Bhagavad Gita offers a rich source for understanding happiness and well-being, which are two underlying principles of positive psychology. The only need is to create awareness of the rich source of wisdom contained in this holy text.

कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्ते मा फलेषु कदाचन
मा कर्मफलहेतुर्भूर्मा ते सङ्गोऽस्त्वकर्मणि
(Bhagavad Gita, chapter II, verse 47)

Verse 47 of Chapter 2 of this holy book explains how individuals should behave without becoming attached to outcomes. A person should give up the pride of doership, as the fruits of actions are not meant for individuals to enjoy. This Hindu scripture has also helped individuals in developing resilience (Tripathi et al., 2025). The Gita encourages treating pain, joy, victory, and defeat equally and accepting failed attempts as a natural part of the process (Bhagavad Gita, 2:15; 12:13). It believes that both positive and negative aspects operate together and cannot be expected to exist independently. Gita equips people to face both positive as well as negative situations, leading to a positive outlook (Gavade, 2022).

Dabbas and Singh (2018) conducted an experimental investigation with Indian upper-middle elementary school pupils. Group 1, the placebo group, was assigned ordinary coursework. Whereas Group 2, the participants in the experiment, received the teachings of the Bhagavad Gita. The study found that Indian interventions boosted positive dimensions of hope, optimism, and resilience among Group 2 pupils. Therefore, the lessons of the Bhagavad Gita have been shown to improve an individual's psychological capital, leading to sustainable employability over time.

Emotional Intelligence and Bhagavad Gita

The next factor that leads to (perceived) sustainable employability

is emotional intelligence. It refers to an individual's mental ability linked to their emotional experiences (Lamba, Jagadeesh, & Deshpande, 2022). The concept was introduced by the seminal work of Salovey and Mayer (1990). They described it as the ability to observe and distinguish one's own and others' emotions, and use this information to steer actions.

Emotional intelligence has been evidenced in the literature relating to employability (Coetzee & Schreuder, 2011). Highly emotionally intelligent individuals can better adapt to their careers. Based on the conservation of resource theory, Liu et al. (2008) found emotional intelligence valuable for individuals as it enhances one's psychological health and well-being. It also affects the employability of a person.

The Bhagavad Gita outlines the path and means to success. It describes how the senses and the intellect work together to create consistent intelligence. According to the Bhagavad Gita, emotional intelligence is the ability to discern where one's emotions should and should not be committed (Gavade, 2022). Emotions are an individual's resources. When one becomes emotionally immersed in anything, one feels greatly energised.

As a result, emotions are both a source as well as a consumer of energy (Lamba et al., 2022). Salagame (2016) also believes that the Bhagavad Gita contains a wide understanding of concepts like well-being, emotional intelligence, and happiness.

Figure 2

The Chronological Order from Gross Body to Soul

Note. (Source: Lamba, Jagadeesh, & Deshpande, 2022)

The Bhagavad Gita teaches how to manage one's body and thoughts. The teaching emphasizes the importance of soul-consciousness in maintaining constant intelligence (see to Figure 2). Remaining deeply aware of one's soul might result in a tranquil mind, self-awareness, and self-regulation, which ultimately impact emotional intelligence (Lamba et al., 2022). It also offers a way for individuals to remove the darkness of emotional instability. It provides answers to questions relating to contemporary dilemmas of a person through a dialogue between emotionally disturbed Arjuna and Lord Krishna (Gayathri & Meenakshi, 2012).

कार्पण्यदोषोपहतस्वभावः

पृच्छामि त्वां धर्मसम्मूढचेताः ।

यद्द्वेयः स्यान्निश्चितं ब्रूहि तन्मे

शिष्यस्तेऽहं शाधि मां त्वां प्रपन्नम्

(Bhagavad Gita, chapter II, verse 7) Verse 7 of Chapter II of the Bhagavad Gita reveals cowardice in the behaviour of Arjuna's mind. Arjuna pleads for help from Lord Krishna for instructing him about the path of auspiciousness.

स्थितप्रज्ञस्य का भाषा समाधिस्थस्य केशव

स्थितधीः किं प्रभाषेत किमासीत् ब्रजेत किम्

(Bhagavad Gita, Chapter II, verse 54)

In Chapter 2, verse 54 of the Bhagavad Gita, it's described as a state of steady intellect, where an individual has truly conquered the mind and achieved inner balance senses. The person in this state is empathetic, understands oneself, self-regulated, unshaken by pleasure or pain, loss or gain and has complete self-awareness. A person in this *sthitaprajna* state should do actions without any attachment as described in chapter II, sloka 62 of Bhagavad Gita.

Attachment is a root cause of emotional instability and all misery. A person should detach himself from the 'unreal' world as nothing is permanent in this world. Only the soul is real. A *sthitaprajna* soul knows how to distinguish between 'real' and 'unreal' (Bhagavad Gita 2:16; 2:55). The only path to emotional stability is to remain unattached. A person becomes a 'karma yogi' when they learn to do obligatory duties without expecting anything in return. This leads to a high state of emotional intelligence (Gavade, 2022).

Mindfulness and Bhagavad Gita

The concept of mindfulness originated from the Buddhist tradition approximately 2500 years ago (Jabeen et al., 2021). Mindfulness enhances individuals' ability to appraise current market realities and utilise their skills effectively, leading to job retention or improved opportunities (Brown & Ryan, 2003). Individuals who acquire these skills can better regulate their emotions and make informed decisions (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). It is a cognitive skill that enhances employees' psychological well-being. Mindfulness helps individuals evaluate current market situations more effectively and utilise their capabilities sufficiently to keep a job or find better alternatives. As a result, individuals with mindfulness are considered more employable (Jabeen et al., 2021). It also promotes career development capabilities (Lee, 2019).

ध्यायतो विषयान्पुंसः सङ्गस्तेषूपजायते ।

सङ्गात्सञ्जायते कामः कामात्क्रोधोऽभिजायते

(Bhagavad Gita, chapter II, verse 62)

The Bhagavad Gita offers several ways to attain the highest state of mindfulness. Mindfulness can help achieve *Stithaprajna*, which is characterised by unperturbedness, self-regulation, and self-awareness (Kadian, 2024). Verse 62 of chapter II explains attachment as the root cause of all miseries. One should free the mind from attachment because attachment leads to desire and desires give birth to problems like greed and anger.

युञ्जन्नेवं सदात्मानं योगी नियतमानसः ।

शान्तिं निर्वाणपरमां मत्संस्थामधिगच्छति

(Bhagavad Gita, chapter VI, verse 15)

Chapter VI, sloka 15 explains the way to reach the 'mindful state' through meditation that will lead to attaining a calm and un-agitated state. Meditation not only increases concentration but also purifies the mind (Moore & Malinowski, 2009). Mindfulness through meditation creates awareness and helps individuals to pay attention to sensitive and independent thoughts making them better decision-makers, thus leading to their employability (Mani & Mishra, 2023).

Core Self-evaluations and Bhagavad Gita

Core self-evaluations (CSE) are the fundamental assessments of one's value, competency, and aptitude (Judge et al., 2003). Creed and

Gagliardi (2015) described CSE being an important individual asset with four major dimensions (self-esteem, self-efficacy, locus of control, & emotional stability). CSE instills confidence, positivism, and the capacity to adapt well to any circumstance. Such individuals are more engaged in their employment, have a strong feeling of self-importance, and accept more difficult tasks (Judge, Erez, Bono, & Thoresen, 2003; Rich Lepine, & Crawford, 2010). Jabeen et al. (2021) linked High CSE with high sustainable employability.

उद्धरेदात्मनात्मानं नात्मानमवसादयेत् ।

आत्मैव ह्यात्मनो बन्धुरात्मैव रिपुरात्मनः

(Bhagavad Gita, Chapter VI, verse 5)

The Bhagavad Gita, through Chapter VI, Verse 5, inspires an individual to elevate themselves through the power of the mind. The mind can give the ultimate benefits of self-realisation; on the other hand, it has the potential for maximum harm. However, a controlled mind can nurture all beneficial endeavors. By elevating ourselves through our efforts and bringing ourselves to our present state, we can gain self-confidence. The way to attain this state is to understand the functioning of the mind (Kalia et al., 2025). According to Gita, the mind works at four levels, i.e., mind-intellect-chitta-ego. The mind creates thoughts, Intellect helps in deciding and analysing, chitta refers to one's attachment to an object or person, and the ego is related to pride. Lord Krishna, in chapter II, verse 41, emphasizes the use of intellect to control the mind, leading to better locus control (Bhagavad Gita 2:41). A controlled mind is emotionally stable and makes one confident, which ultimately affects sustainable employability (Fugate et al., 2004).

Career Competencies and Bhagavad Gita

Career competencies (CC) are defined by Akkermans, Brenninkmeijer, Huibers, and Blonk (2013) as knowledge, skills, and abilities developed for career growth. These individuals are intrinsically motivated to achieve perfection, actively seek opportunities, and enhance employability (Blokker et al., 2019; Forrier, Verbruggen, & Cuyper, 2015). Akkermans et al. (2013) also gave three dimensions to CC. To begin, reflective professional competencies are an embodiment of morals, motivation, and enthusiasm. Second, Communicative talents include networking and making professional contacts. Third, behavioural professional abilities are associated with seeking career possibilities and maintaining career management (Jabeen et al., 2021).

The holy scripture, Bhagavad Gita explained three types of *gunas* in chapter IV, verse 10.

वीतरागभयक्रोधा मन्मया मामुपाश्रिताः ।

बहवो ज्ञानतपसा पूता मद्भावमागता

First, *sattva guna* makes individuals peaceful, content, generous, tranquil, and serene. It promotes values and enlightenment of knowledge. Second, individuals having *rajo guna* become passionate, agitated, ambitious, and envious of others' success. Third, *tamo guna* creates laziness, hatred, resentment, violence, and doubt. According to the Bhagavad Gita, these three *gunas* are present in one's mind and keep gaining dominance over each other. The dominance of either *guna* depends on the external environment and internal contemplation of a person (Gavade, 2022).

किं कर्म किमकर्मेति कवयोऽप्यत्र मोहिताः ।

तत्ते कर्म प्रवक्ष्यामि यज्ज्ञात्वा मोक्षसेऽशुभात्

(Bhagavad Gita, chapter IV, verse 16)

According to Chapter IV, sloka 16, persons influenced by *sattva guna* are able to perform their actions with pure intentions, hence their results are uplifting and satisfying. As this *guna* gives birth to wisdom and the ability to differentiate between right and wrong, people are inclined towards intellectual pursuits and values. This *guna* better explain the career competencies.

Conclusion

The concept of sustainability is not limited to natural resources only; it has been extended to human resources as well. The increasing globalization, advances in technologies, and migration policies have presented unlimited options for labor movements across the globe. It becomes necessary for employees to excel in their careers but not at the cost of their health and well-being. With the ever-changing nature of psychological contracts between employer and employee, the ultimate responsibility one one's career has come upon the shoulders of that individual only. Sustainable employability is the individual's capacity to perceive themselves as employable while perpetuating health, well-being, motivation, and quality of work. With the Industrial Revolution set in, the world is driven by materialistic goals only. Having forgotten the values and with complete ignorance of self, one cannot have sustainable employability. This study has taken the help of Srimad Bhagavad Gita in understanding self-esteem, self-confidence, motivation, self-realisation, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, and mindfulness. Incorporating the knowledge of the Bhagavad Gita can lead to a higher level of consciousness and a sense of interconnectedness. Individuals following the path shown by Lord Krishna live in complete harmony, which leads to sustainable growth.

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